

DEVELOPMENTS IN THE CAD-MODELING OF TEXTILE YARNS**Abdurasul Pirnazarov**

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Abstract: This research paper targeted at the 3D simulation of textile yarns. Considerable progress has been made particularly in the simulation of knitting yarn and plain knit cloth. This has prompted a more intricate model of yarn structure based on queuing theory which is given at the end of the study. References are provided for those who wish to understand more of the many ideas and models that have been used throughout the course of this paper.

Keywords: Yarn, Modelling, CAD, Simulation, 3D

Introduction

Despite over sixteen years of attempt, the CAD simulation of accurate textile yarn 3D simulation project continues work in progress and due to the intricacy of the subject and the reactionary character of the industry it will probably continue as such for some time to come. The alternative approach followed by this group can be summed up pretty simply as follows:

When a fabric is to be created and then made it is first necessary to choose acceptable yarn with the needed aesthetic and mechanical attributes. It is therefore natural that if an exact computer simulation of a fabric is to be made, we should begin with the accurate modeling of the component yarn (Cassidy, T. & Grishanov, S., 2008).

As with many basic statements of concept, the implications of this statement are far reaching. Only by getting CAD for yarn simulation correct will CAD for fabric simulation be accurate and subsequently CAD for clothing simulation will become the helpful and required tool that it promises to be.

A point to be explored at this stage is why individuals who designed the early CAD systems choose to start at the fabric stage and not with the same building block utilized by fabric producers the yarn. The answer is fairly straightforward. Symbolic

notation methods for fabric structures were accessible and frequently utilized throughout the textile industry for almost two hundred years before the arrival of personal computers. Indeed, the Jacquard loom is viewed by many as the precursor of the computer and operated a complicated shedding mechanism in response to a manually produced notation. Early developers, therefore, already had manual simulations to use as a basis reference. No comparable notations were available for yarn structures and their mechanical properties were relatively little known despite the sterling efforts of researchers such as Treloar, Hearle, Martindale, Goswami and many more. It is scary to contemplate how much progress they may have achieved had they had access to modern high-powered computers. As it was much of this effort went unheeded but the existing body of work offered a starting point for the YarnCAD team as it was originally founded through a grant from EPSRC (Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council) in 1993.

The purpose of the project was to build a computer model which would accurately replicate a flexible fiber assembly, such as yarn in a three-dimensional form, and had sufficient accuracy to allow it to be incorporated into a knitted or woven fabric simulation. Consequently, a large deal of sophisticated mathematics was involved; for the reader who desires to study these carefully references will be given at each stage but in this paper simply an outline will be given.

Materials and methods

Much of the early thinking about how to do the simulations was published in a conference paper while a more accurate description including the use of a compression model to improve the accuracy of the simulations is given in Grishanov et al. (1997a).

It was vital to construct the strand shape accurately and hence it was assumed that the strand had a consistent linear density (count) along its whole length. In this approach the simulated cross-sectional form will be the same throughout its length and the centre line of a strand will keep a constant distance from the centre of the yarn twist. Each strand in a yarn will follow a helical course along the axis of the yarn according to the accepted geometrical models (Grishanov et al., 2011).

A quadrilateral-mesh approach was applied to construct a wire frame model of the strand surface. In this approach each quadrilateral is specified by 3D co-ordinates of four vertices. Each quadrilateral is in turn divided into two triangles; each triangle is one facet.

The vertex array is built to include the actual x -, y - and z -coordinates of all the vertexes on the mesh surface. In order to start the simulation of the strand surface, the vertex array must be assigned the 3D coordinates which are generated from the starting definition, rotation and translation (Siewe et. Al., 2009).

Colour rendering was employed to reveal the yarn texture. When hues are initially assigned to each strand, they are called intrinsic colours. In order to obtain more realistic images the intrinsic colours are ordered to traverse four steps of rendering.

Together with the triangular facets arrangement, colour rendering was also used to imitate the orientation of the fibres of which the strands were constituted.

The initial version of the YarnCAD system was built using C language with a PHIGS graphics routine on a SUN platform. At that time (1990s) the UNIX operating system was rated ideal for simulation work of this nature. As we will see, this had to alter. Based on the geometrical model, the input specifications of the yarn included: yarn type (spinning system); yarn twist content and direction for both single and plied yarns; number of strands, linear density of strands and specific volume of fibres (Kyosev et. al., 2005). When these specifications were fed into the system the geometrical structure of the yarn was translated into an array of triangular facets indicating the surface of the strands involved. The data of the vertex coordinates were supplied onto the yarn modeller to obtain the simulated yarn appearance with a simulated yarn texture as illustrated in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Simulated image of a multiplied yarn.

This ended the first stage of YarnCAD development. What distinguished this effort distinct from everything else that existed at that time (1990s) was the capacity to simulate from production specs and to be accurate when compared to the real yarn created from the same specifications. Also the system was able to alter the simulated image using the arrow keys on the keyboard or the directional buttons on the interface to illustrate the genuine 3D nature of the simulation.

Conclusions

The 3D CAD simulation of textile yarns has been the effort of researchers for roughly three decades years. The approach taken by the researchers delivers genuine 3D yarn, fabric and garment simulations and subsequently sustainable textile and garment CAD systems. In recent times the researchers had handled the simulation of color mixture/melange yarns and this has needed a more advanced yarn structure model based on queuing theory. The new structure model has enabled outstanding colour prediction findings which will shortly be published and extremely good 3D simulations of real melange yarns. Resulting from this study new industrial attention is attracted to look at the usage of dope dyed fibres as blends to reduce the number of stock colors necessary and the amount of dyeing at the more environmentally downstream materials.

References

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